

SOME CONSIDERATIONS FROM THE HISTORY OF DEFENSE FACILITIES OF CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotation: Defense structures were one of the determining factors of the process of urbanization of the society. Therefore, solving issues related to the research of defense structures and their development dynamics is one of the urgent problems. The analysis of historical processes in Central Asia consists of the analysis of similar processes in separate historical and cultural regions with fortified settlements, urban centers and fortresses. It played an important role in the historical and cultural events of the entire Central Asia and its surrounding areas.

Keywords: defensive walls, Central Asia, castle, military fortifications, constellations, Kh. Mukhamedov, Shinak, protekhism, ditch, Sughd, Yerkurgan.

Introduction: Central Asia is one of the oldest centers of world civilization. A rich and unique culture has been created by the people of this region. Thanks to the researches of archaeologists and historians, who are looking for the roots of the culture of the peoples of Central Asia, the historical-archeological field is becoming more and more clear. The collection of Zoroastrian religious texts - "Avesta" is a very important source of the oldest history of Central Asia. His first chapter, "Videvdat", contains a list compiled by Ahura Mazda of countries in Central Asia, as well as neighboring Afghanistan and northeastern Iran, including ArvyanamVaija, "Gova, the place of Sughds", "mighty wamo'minMouri (Marv province)", "beautiful Bakhdi (Bactria) whose flags are raised high", "Nisaya between Mouri and Bakhdi", Horaiva (Herot province) and Indus and Harvati (Aroksia) in the southeast other regions up to the territories, Haitumanta in the Helmand valley in the south, Gurganj in the west, Par (in the northeast of Midia) and others are mentioned.

The development and characteristics of the defense structures surrounding the ancient settlements and cities between the two rivers of Central Asia is an important indicator of the level of social development and is one of the urgent problems of the ancient urban civilizations. The most ancient information about the fortresses of Central Asia belongs to the ancient Greek and Roman historians. They depicted the Greco-Persian wars and the conquest of Central Asia by the armies of Alexander the

Great. Ctesius writes about the impregnable fortified places of Bactria, Quintus Kursi Rufus informs that the city of Maroqand, which was the capital of Sughd during the Achaemenid period, was surrounded by a fortress wall; And Arrian, while describing the march of Alexander the Great to Central Asia, writes that the walls of Kyropolis, founded by Cyrus, were the highest and strongest compared to other walls. "Among the many cities in Bactria, there is one wonderful city called Bactra (Balkh), which stands out from all the fortresses because of its size," reports Diodorus. In the 1st century BC, Strabo mentioned the outer walls of Morocco. Chinese sources of the 2nd century report that the wall of the Davan fortress had two floors [1.]. Unfortunately, this information is limited and does not provide accurate information about the ancient military fortifications of Central Asia.

Methods. The archeological study of ancient Central Asian monuments began at the end of the 19th century, after the occupation of this region by Russia. However, this work yielded very little results. Archaeologically, ancient Central Asian monuments began to be truly studied in the 20th century, as well as at the beginning of the 21st century.

In the course of archaeological excavations conducted in the south of Turkmenistan, the defensive structures of Olintepa of the Bronze Age and Erqkala of the Early Iron Age, as well as the system of military fortifications in Parthia - New and Old Nisa, Koyneqala, Govurqala, Devqala, Chilburj and others were discovered. Defense devices of the Bronze Age are also known in Bactria. These are Dashli I, Sopollitepa, Jarqo`ton and others. Sopollitepa is a complex military fortification. The fortress and castle of Jarqo`ton city are also surrounded by a wall. [2.].

Zartepa, Old Termiz, Talashkantepa, Old Castle, Kumtepa, Jigatepa fortifications, settlements in the Vakhsh Valley and others are of great importance in the study of defense devices of Bactria in the early Iron Age.

The research of ancient settlements and defense devices of cities in Sughd began from the city of Tali Barzu. The first fortified structures of Sughd were opened in the cities of Afrosiyab and Yerkurgan. Ancient defense devices of Qal'ai Zakhoki Moron, Varakhsha, Bukhara in ancient Sughd were studied.

In recent years, R. H. Sulaimanov has conducted excavations in the city of Yerkurgan, where there is a monument of Kashkadarya Sugdi. Here, in addition to general information and archeological materials, a lot of facts about architecture were obtained, observation works were carried out. By opening parts of the walls of the Yerkurgan fortress, the process of the construction and changes of the fortifications was determined: BC. In the middle of the 1st millennium, the wall was smooth. avv. By the II century, the wall was reinforced with rectangular towers, in the V-VII centuries, the towers were surrounded by a semi-circular casing [3.].

Ferghana Valley defensive devices consist of Bronze Age and Early Iron Age monuments. These are, among others, Eilatan, Sho`rabashat, Mingtepa and others. It is known that such devices exist in the Chust Valley. In 2003-2004, as a result of the archeological excavation in Fergana area, new material was obtained on the ancient urbanization in Fergana, and Dalvarzin was found to be the first city that stands out among the first cities of Central Asia in the Bronze and Early Iron Ages. Such work was also carried out in Akhsikat, where a military fortification dating back to antiquity was excavated [4].

The process of urbanization associated with strong fortress walls in the Tashkent oasis corresponds to the very end of the Burguluq period.

A long wall was opened in the territory of Central Asia, including Balkh and Darband (Bactria). Similar walls were found in Sug'd (Doomsday Wall), Marv, Parthia.

As a result of these archeological works, a huge amount of material was collected, which made it possible to determine the solution to a number of important and previously unexplored issues of the history of the military fortifications of ancient Central Asia.

However, very few studies have been devoted to the study of ancient Central Asian military architecture. Among them, first of all, it is possible to single out separate articles and researches dedicated to the review of the ancient military fortifications of Central Asia and Central Asia in general. These are: on separate defense structures; on defense systems of all oases; works on countries and Central Asia.

Among them are K. Sabirov, G.P. The studies of Frankfort and M. Turebekov are particularly interesting. In the research of K. Sabirov, the creation of military fortifications in Central Asia and their evolution from the Eneolithic period to the Kushon era were considered. According to the development of defense structures and their functional function and role in ancient society, four main periods are distinguished: primitive, before the appearance of cities, the period of first cities and city military fortifications. In the research of G. Frankfort, the defense structures of settlements and cities in Central Asia (Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Northern Afghanistan and a small part of Khorasan, Iran) from the Bronze Age to the end of the Kushan period is analyzed. H. Mukhamedov proposes to divide them into three main chronological periods: Bronze and Achaemenid period, Hellenic period, Kushon period. [5].

It is known that the emergence and construction of defense structures in the territory of Central Asia did not go smoothly. For example, the first defensive walls around the settlements in South Turkmenistan were raised in the Eneolithic period (Geoksyur settlements) and their construction intensified during the Bronze Age (Altintepa). In the regions of Bactria and Fergana Valley, they began to form in the Bronze Age. When it comes to Sughd and Khorezm regions, there are settlements and

defense structures. avv. It became known from the middle of the 1st millennium. Therefore, the chronological classifications attached by K. Sabirov and G. Frankfort are not always favorable in relation to the local regions of the area under consideration. In the researches of M. Turebekov, defense structures of the ancient settlements and cities of Sughd in the early Middle Ages were described, systematized and summarized. The emergence of ancient settlements and cities, the dynamics of development are considered, four stages of the development of Sughd defense structures are distinguished. These are: The end of the 8th century BC - the 4th century BC. IV-I centuries, I century BC - IV century, IV-VIII centuries. However, some assumptions of the author, including the shape of the bricks of the construction period of Ko`zaliqir II and the date of the construction of Qal`aliqir, date back to BC. Assumptions about marking the end of the IV-II centuries are seriously disputed. [6.]. The transition from rectangular brick to square brick is more related to the influence of the Achaemenid construction technique during the period when Khorezm was part of the ancient Iranian state.

Results. Defense structures were one of the determining factors of the process of urbanization of the society. Therefore, solving issues related to the research of defense structures and their development dynamics is one of the urgent problems. The analysis of the historical processes that took place in Central Asia consists of the analysis of similar processes in separate historical and cultural regions with fortified settlements, urban centers and fortresses. It played an important role in the historical and cultural events of Central Asia and its surrounding areas.

Discussion. It can be seen that in the military architecture of a certain period of ancient Central Asia, the approach to the issue of layout was the same. Castle structures were built based on the requirements of the time and the social and political situation. The characteristic of the period is more reflected in them than in any other type of objects. This is natural, otherwise they would not be able to fulfill their function. It was clear above that fortifications often depend not only on practical requirements, but also on the relief of the place. Like the first fortifications of Central Asia (Afrosiyab, Yerkurgan, Erkkala, etc.), fortifications in other regions of Central Asia were also built in the wrong form. Such a tradition was also recorded in the environment of the nomads (Chirik Rabat and others). [7.]

On the threshold of the 5th-4th centuries BC, states were formed in ancient Central Asia, a unique "urbanization explosion" took place, and a whole series of urban centers appeared. A system of border fortresses and long walls were built on the borders. Nomads were pushed out from the borders of Central Asia, from old villages. But this does not mean that they were divided in war relations with the settlers. The relations of settled peasants and city dwellers with settlers were of two types.

Sometimes they exchanged livestock products peacefully, sometimes they were in a state of war. The people of the steppes used to attack the cities with the aim of looting.

Research conducted in the region's forts revealed that the defense of the oasis was organized, and their fortifications and settlements testify to the development of peaceful relations. It has been determined that the archaeological monuments located in the north-western part of Central Asia were not only fortifications, but also handicraft and trade centers.

The fortifications began to acquire a correct geometric shape. Architects of Central Asia began to build walls more rapidly in a straight line and clearly visible. The shape of the constellations also begins to gain clarity. On the walls of the castle, two-story shooting lanes, protected by a parapet, were made. Walls with battle corridors were developed and formed a necessary part of the defense system throughout antiquity. As evidenced by the preserved materials, there were stairs between the upper and lower floors of the shooting lanes. During this period, the defense of the fortress walls without turrets, based on a complex system of bulwarks placed along the entire wall, was one of the important features of the defense structures of Central Asia.

In the 1st-4th centuries BC, the methods and elements of the defense system of the early antiquity of ancient Central Asia continued to be used in military architecture. It can be considered as one of the unique features of the military architecture of this time that many small fortifications were created.

The types of weapons used by the Bactrians, Sugdians, and Parthians were widely used. It is not an exception that they produced their own weapons, including complex bows, swords, etc.

The development of constructions and forms of defense facilities is directly related to the development of weapons and military equipment. In our opinion, this is clearly expressed in the multi-level defense system of ancient Central Asia. The defense system of Central Asia can be divided into four groups: the first - one-story fortress wall and trench fortifications; the second - fortifications with a passage between the walls and a trench; the third - fortifications with a shooting lane, a protekhism and a trench; the fourth - fortifications with a rampart, a wall with a shooting lane, a protekhism and a ditch.

The phased defense system was apparently designed not only against an enemy consisting of infantry and cavalry, but also against an enemy armed with siege devices. The development of the additional wall (protekhism) and the thickening of the fortress walls can probably be explained by this. In this case, an additional wall (protekhism) was built 5-20 m away from the main line of defense, and the protected area around the fortress wall was expanded. As a result, a target range was created for the defenders of the fortification from bows, self-propelled guns, and slingshots.

During the Battle of the Castle, the provision of water to the population was one of the important problems in the construction of defense structures. Perhaps, this issue was solved in different ways in ancient Central Asia. In some cases, a well was dug inside the fortification, and in other cases, this work was carried out by bringing water through pipes.

Conclusion

In ancient times, a common defense system was formed in Central Asia. When it comes to the coexistence of different types of fortifications, this is due to the fact that the fortifications in Central Asia and the Middle East in general were of the same type at that time. At the same time, as a result of comparing the military architecture of the ancient Middle Asia with the defense structures of the ancient world, it became clear that the generality of the rules of architecture and design in the Middle Asia has a number of unique features. For example, the fortresses of Central Asia are characterized by double walls with internal corridors, various types of front gate structures, two rows of spear-shaped pillars, etc. Side doors in gates; "Swallow's tail" constellations, which are not widely used in other regions of Central Asia, are a unique method of the ancient Central Asian defense system. These serve as proof that the defense system in Central Asia is mainly developed on a local basis. It is even possible that Central Asia has influenced other regions in terms of some elements and methods of construction of defense structures, including front gate diversion route, shooting lane, etc.

Thus, in ancient times, the art of defense structures of ancient Central Asia was at the level of the art of defense structures of Central Asia. It can be said that there was a school of construction of fortified structures here.

As a conclusion, it should be noted that the ancient military architecture of Central Asia was not the last point of the development of the urbanization process in the region. Later, the feudal defense structures of the early Middle Ages and the Middle Ages appeared. At the same time, the military fortifications of the early Middle Ages and the Middle Ages have preserved many elements of older times. Determining this succession is an important task for researchers.

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